

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

THE IMPORTANCE AND MAIN STAGES OF CREATING AN E-COMMERCE WEBSITE

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ABSTRACT

As a result of globalization and the rapid development of internet technologies, commercial activity has entered a new phase. Electronic commerce (e-commerce) allows both businesses and consumers to access wider markets at lower costs by eliminating time and space constraints. The study explains the types of e-commerce, especially B2B, B2C, C2C and C2G models. It also outlines consumer expectations from websites – criteria such as accuracy, reliability, interactivity, responsiveness, usability and modernity. The study analyzes the stages of creation and reasons for success of successful e-commerce websites such as Amazon, Etsy, Alibaba, eBay and Trendyol. The aim is to explain the importance of e-commerce websites and their creation processes.

Keywords: E-commerce, website, modern trends, stages of websites.

Introduction

Relevance of the study: The globalization, economic, cultural, and social boundaries have disappeared, and barriers to information and trade have diminished. In this context, internet technologies, one of the most important actors in this process with their rapid development and worldwide prevalence, have taken commerce to a new dimension. The resulting transition to a new economy based on e-commerce is rapidly spreading due to the benefits it provides to both businesses and consumers. As a natural consequence of this situation, while the development of internet technologies is accelerating, new applications interacting with e-commerce, especially social media, are also emerging. In this context, businesses seeking to succeed in the new economy are not only opting for e-commerce but also developing their web and social networking sites in line with developing technology and changing consumer expectations. This study first explains the concepts and developments of e-commerce, websites, and social media, and provides information about consumer expectations from web and social networking sites. Then, the data obtained from the content analysis of e-commerce businesses' web and social networking sites is evaluated, and various recommendations are made accordingly for new and existing e-commerce businesses. With the development of the new economy and the rapid increase in information technology applications, the concept of electronic commerce (e-commerce) is gaining more widespread use. The advantages of e-commerce, particularly its relatively low costs, its elimination of time and space limitations, and its ability to enable the interactive and simultaneous transmission of various types of text (audio, video, text, etc.) by multiple individuals, have led to its rapid rise to prominence. According to Sarisakal, another reason for the increased use of e-commerce is the increasing prevalence of retail sales, particularly in the developing internet environment. E-commerce has been defined in different ways by different individuals and institutions, but a common definition of e-commerce has not yet been reached. E-commerce, also known as the new name for commerce influenced by advancing technol-

ogy in modern times, can be defined as the buying, selling, ordering, and sometimes delivery of products electronically, usually over a network. In its simplest form, e-commerce is the improvement of business performance through computer networks. As a result, businesses benefit from increased profitability, increased market share, improved customer service, and expanded distribution channels. However, this definition should not be interpreted as simply ordering products from an online catalog. On the contrary, e-commerce encompasses the use of information technologies to enhance business operations and communication with all stakeholders (customers, suppliers, government, employees, managers, etc.).

The types of e-commerce are as follows:

➤ **Business-to-Business e-commerce (B2B):** Business processes such as purchasing from suppliers, issuing invoices, and making payments occur electronically between businesses. The best example of this type is Alibaba.com, which has enabled China to enter the international market. Research shows that business-to-business commerce accounts for a larger share of total e-commerce than that between businesses and consumers.

➤ **Business-to-Consumer e-commerce (B2C):** This type of e-commerce, which typically involves businesses providing marketing and sales services to consumers through virtual stores, is best implemented by Amazon.com.

➤ **Consumer-to-Consumer e-commerce (C2C):** This type involves purchases made between consumers through trusted websites operating through membership systems. eBay.com is the best international example, and gittigidiyor.com is the best domestic example. **Consumer to Public Institution e-commerce (C2G):** This type of e-commerce, which is the newest among the types of e-commerce, covers all kinds of tax, health and legal activities between the consumer and the public administration, where applications such as driver's license, passport, ID applications or tax payments are carried out, with the aim of ensuring the transition to "electronic government".

Purpose of the study: The main goal of the study is to examine the importance of e-commerce websites today and the stages of their creation.

Literature review

The internet is defined as a communications infrastructure that enables people to communicate and exchange information for various purposes and content, or as a collection of networks that provide reliable, sequential, and end-to-end information transfer through a protocol. This protocol, known as TCP (Transmission Control Protocol) / IP (Internet Protocol), creates a common language, enabling communication between computers over high-capacity telephone lines. The fundamental characteristics of the internet, an interactive tool for information and communication, are accessibility and interaction. By making information readily accessible to everyone through a computer and internet connection, the internet enables interpersonal connections, simultaneous communication, and direct feedback, independent of time and space (Badwaik, D., et.al.,2025).

With developing technology, internet use has become more collaborative, richer, and more social, changing the way consumers work, socialize, and purchase, and enabling them to engage with a brand in various ways. Businesses that fail to capitalize on this process not only miss out on new opportunities, but also lose their competitive edge by failing to build an audience around their brands due to their inability to communicate and interact with customers online. Because online purchasing behavior is in its early stages of development, consumers' knowledge and adoption of e-commerce are limited (Tomić, T., et.al.,2025). Therefore, to foster greater consumer adoption, e-commerce businesses need to understand the factors influencing consumers. While studies indicate that consumers' perceived benefits positively influence their intentions, there are also studies indicating that the complexity that comes with innovation negatively impacts consumers by forcing them to navigate complex organizational interactions. Generally speaking, businesses seeking success in e-commerce must prioritize maximizing the number of online visitors. To build relationships with online consumers, businesses must understand user preferences and how they interact with websites. The next focus should be on determining how to provide a compelling website with the richest content possible, encouraging consumers to shop and return through richer and more unique experiences. As in traditional commerce, marketing components in e-commerce are tailored to consumer desires and needs. Therefore, for a successful marketing strategy, it is crucial to understand the demographic, socio-cultural, and other characteristics of target consumers, as well as their behavioral patterns, the websites they visit, their connections, and their interaction levels. In this context, an important point that should not be overlooked is that, just like businesses that use the web to achieve tangible and intangible benefits, such as enhancing their image and increasing profitability by selling more products and services, consumers also seek to benefit themselves (Chahal, H., 2025). Therefore, businesses should develop

their websites in line with customer expectations and desires. Based on the findings of various studies, the fundamental expectations of online consumers from businesses' websites can be listed as follows:

- Accuracy refers to the accuracy of all information on the site, including the information provided about the product/service.
- Reliability refers to the site's corporate identity and the protection of the privacy of users' personal information.
- Interactivity refers to the ability of users to share their opinions about your product/service and brand with other users, share visual or written content, and provide ongoing customer feedback.
- Responsiveness refers to the rapid response to customer requests and loading speed.
- Usability refers to the provision of understandable and exaggerated information on every page within a logical and intuitive structure, and the overall consistent approach of the website.
- Efficiency refers to customer satisfaction with the time and speed required to perform activities such as searching, finding, ordering, etc. on the website, and the service outcome.
- Experience refers to the enjoyment provided by making the time spent online enjoyable, the primary source of customer repeat visits, through an attractive design created with various links and visually supportive elements.
- Up-to-dateness refers to the pleasure provided by making the time spent online enjoyable. It refers to regularly updated content and immediate responses to customer comments. Businesses should consider the criteria described above when creating their own websites and social media sites, even creating designs and content that align with the expectations of their target audience. Attracting consumers to a website/social network is like attracting them to a store. This is especially important for e-commerce businesses (Patel, A., et.al.,2025).

For businesses wishing to operate in a virtual environment, creating a website offers significant advantages in terms of cost, promotion, and effective marketing. The web, which allows for visual and auditory appeal in addition to written content, is a frequently preferred virtual tool for businesses. Web pages must also have a professional appearance in terms of technical and design. Because social media today offers the opportunity to communicate with large audiences online, activities conducted on Facebook and Twitter, the two most popular social media platforms in the world (Richard, F., et.al.,2025).

Creating an e-commerce website plays an important role in the development of modern business. Such sites create a connection between companies and customers, provide online sales of products and services. A properly planned and technically efficient website helps both increase sales and brand recognition (Luo, L., Takanokura, M., 2025).

Scheme 1. Basic steps of an e-commerce website

Source: Prepared by the author himself based on various sources.

Creating an e-commerce website consists of several main stages:

1. Defining the goal

At the first stage, the main goal and functions of the site are determined. Why is the site being created, what products and services will it offer, who is it intended for - these questions must be answered clearly. If the goal is not clearly defined, it becomes difficult to successfully complete the project.

2. Determining the target audience

It is very important to know who the website is intended for. The age group, interests and needs of the audience directly affect the design and content development.

3. Competitor analysis

Before developing a site, the websites of competitors operating in the same field should be studied. This helps to determine which services and design elements are more successful in the market.

4. Keyword Selection

It is important to determine the right keywords for the site to be easily found in search engines. This increases the SEO (search engine optimization) level of the site and attracts more users.

5. Design and technical structure preparation

At this stage, the appearance of the site, menus, colors and functions are prepared. A design suitable for mobile devices and a simple interface increase customer satisfaction.

6. Integration of security and payment systems

Data protection and secure payment mechanisms are the main conditions for e-commerce sites. SSL certificate, reliable payment platforms and data encryption play an important role in this area.

7. Testing and commissioning

After the site is fully ready, the functionality of all functions is checked and it is commissioned after the testing phase.

Successful e-commerce websites

In the modern era, the importance of e-commerce websites is increasing. These sites directly connect buyers and sellers, facilitate shopping and create a competitive advantage in the global market. The success of e-commerce systems depends on the technical, design and marketing strategies of a properly built website. The most well-known e-commerce platforms in the world, Amazon, Etsy, Alibaba, eBay and Trendyol, are considered exemplary models in this field (Pai, C. S., et.al., 2025; Amany, S., 2025).

Amazon

Amazon is the largest e-commerce company in the world. Founded by Jeff Bezos in 1994, Amazon initially started as an online bookstore and later became a giant platform covering all product categories. In 2024, Amazon's annual revenue exceeded 570 billion US dollars. The company's success is due to its strong website infrastructure, fast logistics system and customer-oriented policy. The Amazon website provides users with a simple interface, filters for product search, customer reviews and a secure payment system. These elements are key steps to increasing the effectiveness and customer satisfaction of your e-commerce website (<https://www.amazon.com/>).

Etsy

Etsy is a platform created for selling personal and handmade products. Launched in 2005, Etsy enables small businesses and artisans to offer their products to international buyers. Etsy's revenue in 2024 was approximately \$2.8 billion. Etsy's success lies in its design simplicity and community-based approach. The

main goal when creating the site was to establish a personal connection between the buyer and the seller, to highlight the uniqueness of the product. This type of e-commerce website model is built on differentiation and creativity. The quality of product descriptions, image layout and ease of use on Etsy have a significant impact on increasing sales (<https://www.etsy.com/>).

Alibaba

Alibaba is a Chinese-origin, world's largest B2B (business-to-business) e-commerce platform. Founded in 1999 by Jack Ma. The company strengthens global trade relations by integrating both wholesale and retail sales systems. In 2024, Alibaba Group's total revenue was close to \$130 billion. Its website has a multilingual interface, a fast product search engine, and a reliable trade guarantee. One of the key stages in the creation of Alibaba's website was the integration of security systems and the adaptation of international payment methods. This platform is an important example of how e-commerce sites should be built on a global scale (<https://www.alibaba.com/>).

eBay

Established in 1995, eBay is the first e-commerce site to introduce the online auction system to the world. Here, users can sell and buy both new and used products. eBay's annual revenue in 2024 was approximately \$10 billion. The success of the site is based on its simple design, auction system, and international delivery capabilities. One of the key stages in the creation of the eBay website was the security of user accounts and the transparency of the buying and selling process. To gain the trust of customers, the site uses customer ratings and a seller rating system (<https://www.ebay.com/>).

Trendyol

Trendyol is one of the largest e-commerce platforms in Turkey and was founded in 2010. It mainly sells fashion, technology and everyday products online. In 2024, Trendyol's revenue exceeded 5 billion US dollars. Trendyol's success is due to its design and ease of use adapted to the requirements of the local market. Fast delivery, visual design of discount campaigns and quality of customer service were among the main stages in the creation of the site. The mobile application is also integrated with the website, providing users with a more convenient shopping experience (<https://www.trendyol.com/>).

Conclusion

The study shows that e-commerce has become one of the main driving forces of the modern economy. With the development of Internet technologies and the expansion of social media, new opportunities have emerged for companies, and competition has become more global. The main conditions for creating successful e-commerce sites are the correct definition of the

goal, identification of the target audience, competitor analysis and integration of secure payment systems. The examples mentioned in the study Amazon, Etsy, Alibaba, eBay and Trendyol show that a simple interface, fast service and customer satisfaction are the main keys to success. In order to succeed in the digital environment, enterprises must adapt their site design and content to consumer expectations. At the same time, the integration of social media platforms allows companies to reach a wider audience and increase brand recognition. As a result, properly planned and technically efficient e-commerce sites create conditions for increasing sales, expanding market share and forming long-term customer loyalty.

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